

Cite this: *Metallomics*, 2018,
10, 768

Correction: Reactions of metallodrugs with proteins: selective binding of phosphane-based platinum(II) dichlorides to horse heart cytochrome c probed by ESI MS coupled to enzymatic cleavage

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DOI: 10.1039/c8mt90014k

rsc.li/metallomics

Correction for 'Reactions of metallodrugs with proteins: selective binding of phosphane-based platinum(II) dichlorides to horse heart cytochrome c probed by ESI MS coupled to enzymatic cleavage' by Carolin Mügge *et al.*, *Metallomics*, 2011, **3**, 987–990.

The surname of the second author was incorrect in the published version of the paper; the corrected version is shown above.
The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

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